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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ATOMOXETINE HCL
SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLETS**K.Sai Varsha^{1*}, Dr.J.Ramesh¹¹Department Of Pharmaceutics, Omega College Of Pharmacy, Edulabad, Hyderabad (Telangana)**Article Received: August 2024****Accepted: September 2024****Published: October 2024****Abstract:**

The objective of the present study was to develop a sustained release matrix tablets of Atomoxetine Hcl an hyperactivity disorder. The sustained release tablets were prepared by direct compression method and formulated using different polymer ratios formulation such as AH1 to AH 9 polymers like HPMC K100M, Ethyl cellulose and Xanthan gum were used compatibility of the drug with various excipients was studied. The compressed tablets were evaluated and showed compliance with pharmacopoeial limits. The optimized formulation AH4 on basis of acceptable tablet properties and in vitro drug release. The resulting formulation produced robust tablets optimum hardness, consistent weight uniformity and friability. All tablets were sustained release for Atomoxetine Hcl for 12hrs among all the nine formulations AH4 showed 99.23% for 12hrs and consider as a optimized formulation.

Keywords: Atomoxetine Hcl, sustained release tablets**Corresponding author:****K.Sai Varsha,**

Department of Pharmaceutics, Omega college of pharmacy,

Edulabad, Hyderabad (Telangana),

Email Id- Saivarshasaivarsha2809@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

A drug delivery system (DDS) is defined as a formulation or a device that enables the introduction of a therapeutic substance in the body and improves its efficacy and safety by controlling the rate, time, and place of release of drugs in the body [1]. This process includes the administration of the therapeutic product, the release of the active ingredients by the product, and the subsequent transport of the active ingredients across the biological membranes to the site of action [2,3]. The term therapeutic substance also applies to an agent such as gene therapy that will induce in vivo production of the active therapeutic agent. Sustained release tablets are commonly taken only once or twice daily, compared with counterpart conventional forms that may have to take three or four times daily to achieve the same therapeutic effect [4]. The advantage of administering a single dose of a drug that is released over an extended period of time to maintain a near-constant or uniform blood level of a drug often translates into better patient compliance, as well as enhanced clinical efficacy of the drug for its intended use [5,6].

The first sustained release tablets were made by Howard Press in New Jersey in the early 1950's. The first tablets released under his process patent were called 'Nitroglyn' and made under license by Key Corp. in Florida.

Sustained release, prolonged release, modified release, extended release or depot formulations are terms used to identify drug delivery systems that are designed to achieve or extend therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose.

The goal in designing sustained or sustained delivery systems is to reduce the frequency of the dosing or to increase effectiveness of the drug by localization at the site of action, reducing the dose required or providing uniform drug delivery. So, sustained release dosage form is a dosage form that release one or more drugs continuously in predetermined pattern for a fixed period of time, either systemically or to a specified target organ [7,8].

Sustained release dosage forms provide a better control of plasma drug levels, less dosage frequency, less side effect, increased efficacy and constant delivery. There are certain considerations for the preparation of extended release formulations:

- If the active compound has a long half-life, it is sustained on its own,

- If the pharmacological activity of the active is not directly related to its blood levels,
- If the absorption of the drug involves an active transport and
- If the active compound has very short half-life then it would require a large amount of drug to maintain a prolonged effective dose.

The above factors need serious review prior to design.

Introduction of matrix tablet as sustained release (SR) has given a new breakthrough for novel drug delivery system in the field of Pharmaceutical technology. It excludes complex production procedures such as coating and Pelletization during manufacturing and drug release rate from the dosage form is controlled mainly by the type and proportion of polymer used in the preparations. Hydrophilic polymer matrix is widely used for formulating an SR dosage form. Because of increased complication and expense involved in marketing of new drug entities, has focused greater attention on development of sustained release or controlled release drug delivery systems. Matrix systems are widely used for the purpose of sustained release. It is the release system which prolongs and controls the release of the drug that is dissolved or dispersed [9].

In fact, a matrix is defined as a well-mixed composite of one or more drugs with gelling agent i.e. hydrophilic polymers. By the sustained release method therapeutically effective concentration can be achieved in the systemic circulation over an extended period of time, thus achieving better compliance of patients. Numerous SR oral dosage forms such as membrane controlled system, matrices with water soluble/insoluble polymers or waxes and osmotic systems have been developed, intense research has recently focused on the designation of SR systems for poorly water soluble drugs.

Rationale for extended release dosage forms:

Some drugs are inherently long lasting and require only once-a-day oral dosing to sustain adequate drug blood levels and the desired therapeutic effect. These drugs are formulated in the conventional manner in immediate release dosage forms. However, many other drugs are not inherently long lasting and require multiple daily dosing to achieve the desired therapeutic results. Multiple daily dosing is inconvenient for the patient and can result in missed doses, made up doses, and noncompliance with the regimen [10,11]. When conventional immediate-release dosage forms are taken on schedule and more

than once daily, they cause sequential therapeutic blood level peaks and valleys (troughs) associated with the taking of each dose. However, when doses are not administered on schedule, the resulting peaks and valleys reflect less than optimum drug therapy. For example, if doses are administered too frequently, minimum toxic concentrations of drug may be reached, with toxic side effects resulting. If doses are missed, periods of sub therapeutic drug blood levels or those below the minimum effective concentration may result, with no benefit to the patient. Extended-release tablets and capsules are commonly taken only once or twice daily, compared with counterpart conventional

forms that may have to be taken three or four times daily to achieve the same therapeutic effect. Typically, extended-release products provide an immediate release of drug that promptly produces the desired therapeutic effect, followed by gradual release of additional amounts of drug to maintain this effect over a predetermined period (Fig.1).

The sustained plasma drug levels provided by extended-release products oftentimes eliminate the need for night dosing, which benefits not only the patient but the caregiver as well [12].

Figure 1.1: Hypothetical plasma concentration-time profile from conventional multiple dosing and single doses of sustained and controlled delivery formulations.

Advantages of sustained release dosage forms

- The frequency of drug administration is reduced.
- Patient compliance can be improved.
- Drug administration can be made more convenient as well.
- The blood level oscillation characteristic of multiple dosing of conventional dosage forms is reduced.
- Better control of drug absorption can be attained, since the high blood level peaks that may be observed after administration of a dose of a high availability drug can be reduced.
- The characteristic blood level variations due to multiple dosing of conventional dosage forms can be reduced.
- The total amount of drug administered can be reduced, thus:
 - Maximizing availability with minimum dose;
 - Minimize or eliminate local side effects;
 - Minimize or eliminate systemic side effects;
 - Minimize drug accumulation with chronic dosing.
- Safety margins of high potency drugs can be increased a the incidence of both local and systemic adverse side effects can be reduced in sensitive patients.
- Improve efficiency in treatment.
 - Cure or control condition more promptly
 - Improve control of condition
 - Improve bioavailability of some drugs
 - Make use of special effects; e.g. sustain release aspirin for morning relief of arthritis by dosing before bed-time.

Disadvantages of sustained release dosage forms:

- Probability of dose dumping.
- Reduced potential for dose adjustment.

- Cost of single unit higher than conventional dosage forms.
- Increase potential for first pass metabolism.
- Requirement for additional patient education for proper medication.
- Decreased systemic availability in comparison to immediate release conventional dosage forms.
- Poor *invitro* and *invivo* correlations.

Terminology:

Modified release delivery systems may be divided conveniently in to four categories.

- A) Delayed release
- B) Sustained release
 - ✓ Controlled release
 - ✓ Extended release
- C) Site specific targeting
- D) Receptor targeting

A) Delayed Release:

These systems are those that use repetitive, intermittent dosing of a drug from one or more immediate release units incorporated into a single dosage form. Examples of delayed release systems include repeat action tablets and capsules and enteric-coated tablets where timed release is achieved by a barrier coating¹⁴.

B) Sustained release:

During the last two decades there has been remarkable increase in interest in sustained release drug delivery system. This has been due to various factor viz. the prohibitive cost of developing new drug entities, expiration of existing international patents, discovery of new polymeric materials suitable for prolonging the drug release, and the improvement in therapeutic efficiency and safety achieved by these delivery systems. Now-a-days the technology of sustained release is also being applied to veterinary products. These systems also provide a slow release of drug over an extended period of time and also can provide some control, whether this be of a temporal or spatial nature, or both, of drug release in the body, or in other words, the system is successful at maintaining constant drug levels in the target tissue or cells¹⁵.

Controlled Release:

These systems include any drug delivery system that achieves slow release of drug over an extended period of time.

Extended Release:

Pharmaceutical dosage forms release the drug slower than normal manner at predetermined rate & necessarily reduce the dosage frequency by two folds.

C) Site specific targeting:

These systems refer to targeting of a drug directly to a certain biological location. In this case the target is adjacent to or in the diseased organ or tissue.

D) Receptor targeting:

These systems refer to targeting of a drug directly to a certain biological location. In this case the target is the particular receptor for a drug within an organ or tissue. Site specific targeting and receptor targeting systems satisfy the spatial aspect of drug delivery and are also considered to be sustained drug delivery systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Atomoxetine Hcl-Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, HPMC K100M-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Ethyl cellulose Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Xanthan gum-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, PVP-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Talc-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, Magnesium Stearate-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India, MCC-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY:

Analytical method development:

a) Determination of absorption maxima:

100mg of Atomoxetine Hcl pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1). 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCL (stock solution-2 i.e., 100µg/ml). From this 10ml was taken and make up with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCL (10µg/ml). Scan the 10µg/ml using Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer in the range of 200 – 400 nm.

b) Preparation calibration curve:

100mg of Atomoxetine Hcl pure drug was dissolved in 15ml of Methanol and volume make up to 100ml with 0.1N HCL (stock solution-1). 10ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCL (Stock solution-2 i.e. 100µg/ml). From this take 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2 and 2.5 ml of solution and make up to 10ml with 0.1N HCL to obtain 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25µg/ml of Atomoxetine Hcl per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 225nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCL as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R^2) which determined by least-square linear regression

analysis. The above procedure was repeated by using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions.

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy:

Drug excipient interaction studies are significant for the successful formulation of every dosage form. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy studies were used for the assessment of physicochemical compatibility and interactions, which helps in the prediction of interaction between drug and other excipients. In the current study 1:1 ratio was used for preparation of physical mixtures used for analyzing of compatibility studies. FT-IR studies were carried out with a Bruker, ATR FTIR facility using direct sample technique.

Formulation development of Sustained release Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by Wet granulation method. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Famotidine.

Procedure:

- Atomoxetine Hcl and all other ingredients except Mg stearate and Talc were individually passed through sieve no \neq 40.
- Atomoxetine Hcl, MCC, and polymer mix thoroughly than add the binder solution mix properly up to 15 min.
- Dry the above mixture at 65-70°C by using dryer.
- After completion of drying the mixture is passed through sieve no \neq 22.
- The powder mixture was lubricated with Mg stearate and Talc.
- Finally go for compression.

Table: Formulation of Sustained release tablets

Ingredients	AH1	AH2	AH3	AH4	AH5	AH6	AH7	AH8	AH9
Atomoxetine Hcl	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
HPMC K100M	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ethyl cellulose	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-	-
Xanthan gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40	60
PVP	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Talc	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Magnesium Stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
MCC	66	46	26	66	46	26	66	46	26
Total weight	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The present work was designed to developing Sustained tablets of Atomoxetine Hcl using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and *in vitro* drug release studies.

The scanning of the 10 μ g/ml solution of Atomoxetine Hcl in the ultraviolet range (200-400nm) against 0.1 N HCL the maximum peak observed at λ_{max} as 225 nm. The standard concentrations of Atomoxetine Hcl (5-25 μ g/ml) was prepared in 0.1N HCL showed good linearity with R² value of 0.997, which suggests that it obeys the Beer-Lamberts law.

Analytical Method:

Standard graph of Atomoxetine Hcl in 0.1N HCL:

Table : Standard curve of Atomoxetine Hcl in 0.1N HCL

Concentration (μ g/ ml)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.104
10	0.212
15	0.321
20	0.418
25	0.532

Fig: Calibration curve of Atomoxetine Hcl in 0.1 N HCL at 225nm

Standard Curve of Atomoxetine Hcl in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8:

The scanning of the 10µg/ml solution of Atomoxetine Hcl in the ultraviolet range (200-400nm) against 6.8 pH phosphate the maximum peak observed at the λ_{max} as 225nm. The standard concentrations of Atomoxetine Hcl (5-25µg/ml) prepared in 6.8 pH phosphate buffer showed good linearity with R^2 value of 0.998, which suggests that it obeys the Beer-Lamberts law

Table: Standard curve of Atomoxetine Hcl in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Concentration (µg / ml)	Absorbance
0	0
5	0.124
10	0.234
15	0.348
20	0.462
25	0.575

Fig: Calibration of Atomoxetine Hcl in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Drug and Excipient Compatibility Studies FTIR study

Fig: FTIR GRAPH OF PURE DRUG

Fig: FTIR GRAPH OF OPTIMISED FORMULATION

From the FTIR data it was evident that the drug and excipients does not have any interactions. Hence they were compatible.

Evaluation parameters:

Pre-compression parameters:

Table: Pre-compression parameters of powder blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
AH1	25.5±0.86	0.15±0.02	0.17±0.02	11.8±0.45	1.14±0.05
AH2	24.4±0.79	0.16±0.01	0.19±0.01	14.3±0.65	1.18±0.02
AH3	22.4±0.79	0.15±0.03	0.18±0.03	16.4±0.9	1.20±0.01
AH4	25.6±0.79	0.16±0.03	0.20±0.02	20.2±0.97	1.23±0.07
AH5	26.9±0.55	0.15±0.02	0.17±0.02	11.9±0.67	1.13±0.03
AH6	25.7±0.6	0.13±0.01	0.15±0.01	12.3±0.96	1.14±0.03
AH7	24.7±1.05	0.14±0.03	0.17±0.02	20.1±0.90	1.12±0.02
AH8	25.5±0.83	0.16±0.02	0.18±0.03	11.3±0.73	1.12±0.01
AH9	27.3±1.25	0.17±0.02	0.21±0.01	15.2±1.11	1.17±0.02

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-compression parameters. The angle of repose values was showed from 25 to 30; it indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.13±0.01 to 0.17±0.02 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.15±0.01 to 0.21±0.01 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be ranging from 11 to 14.28 which showed that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations were showed the hausner ratio ranging from 0 to 1.25 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Post Compression Parameters For tablets

Table: Post Compression Parameters of Tablets

Formulation codes	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (% loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
AH1	200.23 ±0.25	4.8±0.03	0.52±0.03	4.7±0.04	103.5 ± 0.14
AH2	201.53 ± 0.34	4.5±0.02	0.56±0.03	4.2 ±0.02	99.50 ± 0.22
AH3	199.25 ± 2.02	4.6±0.09	0.48±0.08	4.6 ±0.09	104.3 ± 0.12
AH4	198.25± 1.15	4.7±0.01	0.45±0.02	4.3 ±0.05	97.2 ± 0.19
AH5	202.5 ± 0.86	4.7±0.04	0.55±0.07	4.3 ±0.05	98.3 ± 0.20
AH6	203.26 ± 1.25	4.7±0.01	0.45±0.02	4.4±0.05	98.2 ± 0.19
AH7	199.5 ± 0.95	4.8±0.07	0.51±0.04	4.3 ±0.03	102.3 ± 0.28
AH8	202.26 ± 0.81	4.5±0.01	0.55±0.02	4.6±0.06	98.2 ± 0.15
AH9	201.36 ± 1.17	4.7±0.04	0.56±0.04	4.7±0.08	100.8 ± 0.17

Weight variation and thickness:

All the formulations were evaluated for uniformity of weight using electronic weighing balance and the results are shown in table 9.5. The average tablet weight of all the formulations was found to be between $198.25 \pm 1.15 \pm 2.02$ to 203.26 ± 1.25 . The maximum allowed percentage weight variation for tablets weighing >200 mg is 5% and no formulations are not exceeding this limit. Thus all the formulations were found to comply with the standards given in I.P. And thickness of all the formulations was also complying with the standards that were found to be between 4.5 ± 0.01 to 4.8 ± 0.04 .

Hardness and friability:

All the formulations were evaluated for their hardness, using Monsanto hardness tester and the results are shown in table 9.5. The average hardness for all the formulations was found to be between $(4.5 \pm 0.01$ to $4.8 \pm 0.07)$ Kg/cm² which was found to be acceptable.

Friability was determined to estimate the ability of the tablets to withstand the abrasion during packing,

handling and transporting. All the formulations were evaluated for their percentage friability using Roche friabilator and the results were shown in table 9.5. The average percentage friability for all the formulations was between 0.45 ± 0.04 and 0.56 ± 0.04 , which was found to be within the limit.

Drug content:

All the formulations were evaluated for drug content according to the procedure described in methodology section and the results were shown in table 9.5. The drug content values for all the formulations were found to be in the range of $(97.2 \pm 0.19$ to $104.3 \pm 0.12)$. According to IP standards the tablets must contain not less than 95% and not more than 105% of the stated amount of the drug. Thus, all the FDT formulations comply with the standards given in IP.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies:

The formulations prepared with different polymers by direct compression method. The tablets dissolution study was carried out in paddle dissolution apparatus using 0.1N HCL for 2 hours and 6.8 pH phosphate buffers for remaining hours as a dissolution medium.

Table: Dissolution Data of Atomoxetine Hcl Tablets Prepared with HPMC K100M in Different Ratios

TIME (hr)	CUMULATIVE PERCENT DRUG RELEASED		
	AH1	AH2	AH3
0	0	0	0
0.5	14.01	18.32	17.45
1	18.61	24.65	23.06
2	22.08	28.63	28.54
3	29.52	32.84	35.94
4	32.26	39.65	42.23
5	37.78	45.48	49.28
6	46.55	50.95	52.72
7	49.02	53.56	59.05
8	53.54	58.21	62.32
9	59.65	62.65	68.45
10	63.52	67.52	74.04
11	69.02	74.65	79.63
12	76.63	79.43	85.52

Figure: Dissolution study of Atomoxetine Hcl Sustained tablets (AH1 to AH3)

The % drug release of formulations (AH1 to AH3) containing HPMC K100M depends on the concentration of polymer. The concentration of HPMC K100M AH3 release 85.52% for 12hrs.

Table: Dissolution Data of Atomoxetine Hcl Tablets Prepared With Ethyl cellulose in Different Concentrations

TIME (hr)	CUMULATIVE PERCENT DRUG RELEASED		
	AH4	AH5	AH6
0	0	0	0
0.5	16.54	13.64	19.23
1	22.21	18.23	22.06
2	26.26	29.26	27.02
3	29.04	34.52	35.54
4	32.87	43.05	40.55
5	48.63	49.54	44.78
6	54.54	53.29	51.52
7	61.89	59.26	55.23
8	68.07	62.13	59.65
9	76.54	66.23	65.36
10	80.65	69.74	71.65
11	86.45	78.06	78.87
12	99.23	89.41	95.27

Figure : Dissolution study of Atomoxetine Hcl tablets (AH4 to AH6)

The % drug release of AH4 to AH6 formulations depends on ratio of polymer in the solution. The concentration of Ethyl cellulose polymer AH4 release 99.23% for 12hrs

Table : Dissolution Data of Atomoxetine Hcl by using Xanthan gum

TIME (hr)	CUMULATIVE PERCENT DRUG RELEASED		
	AH7	AH8	AH9
0	0	0	0
0.5	17.58	15.25	16.12
1	24.14	23.29	24.51
2	26.53	25.56	29.22
3	31.62	32.65	36.87
4	37.76	47.78	45.52
5	46.15	57.24	49.54
6	59.91	68.08	54.56
7	62.87	72.82	58.85
8	67.26	75.48	63.65
9	76.98	77.96	68.56
10	79.65	82.32	75.78
11	84.78	88.03	78.55
12	92.03	90.33	89.48

Figure : Dissolution study of Atomoxetine Hcl tablets with different ratios of Xanthan gum (AH7 to AH9)

The % drug release of AH7to AH9 formulations depends on ratios of polymer in the solution. The Xanthan gum drug release of AH7 was 92.03% for 12hrs

Hence based on dissolution data of 9formulations, AH4 formulation showed better release (99.23%) up to 12 hours. So AH4 formulation is optimised formulation.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Data of *in vitro* release studies of formulations which were showing better drug release were fit into different equations to explain the release kinetics of Famotidine release from Sustained tablets. The data was fitted into various kinetic models such as zero, first order kinetics; higuchi and korsmeyer peppas mechanisms and the results were shown in below table.

Table : Release kinetics data for optimized formulation (AH4)

CUMULATIVE(%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE/ t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
16.54	0.5	0.707	1.219	-0.301	1.921	33.080	0.0605	-0.781	83.46	4.642	4.370	0.271
22.21	1	1.000	1.347	0.000	1.891	22.210	0.0450	-0.653	77.79	4.642	4.269	0.373
26.26	2	1.414	1.419	0.301	1.868	13.130	0.0381	-0.581	73.74	4.642	4.193	0.448
29.04	3	1.732	1.463	0.477	1.851	9.680	0.0344	-0.537	70.96	4.642	4.140	0.502
32.87	4	2.000	1.517	0.602	1.827	8.218	0.0304	-0.483	67.13	4.642	4.064	0.577
48.63	5	2.236	1.687	0.699	1.711	9.726	0.0206	-0.313	51.37	4.642	3.717	0.924
54.54	6	2.449	1.737	0.778	1.658	9.090	0.0183	-0.263	45.46	4.642	3.569	1.073
61.89	7	2.646	1.792	0.845	1.581	8.841	0.0162	-0.208	38.11	4.642	3.365	1.276
68.07	8	2.828	1.833	0.903	1.504	8.509	0.0147	-0.167	31.93	4.642	3.172	1.469
76.54	9	3.000	1.884	0.954	1.370	8.504	0.0131	-0.116	23.46	4.642	2.863	1.779
80.65	10	3.162	1.907	1.000	1.287	8.065	0.0124	-0.093	19.35	4.642	2.685	1.957
86.45	11	3.317	1.937	1.041	1.132	7.859	0.0116	-0.063	13.55	4.642	2.384	2.258
99.23	12	3.464	1.997	1.079	-0.114	8.269	0.0101	-0.003	0.77	4.642	0.917	3.725

Figure: Graph of Zero order kinetics

Figure : Graph of Higuchi release kinetics

Figure: Graph of Peppas release kinetics

Figure: Graph of First order release kinetics

Based on the data above results the optimized formulation followed Higuchi release kinetics.

CONCLUSION:

The present work was formulation and evaluation of sustained release tablet of Atomoxetine Hcl drug. The main aim of this research work is develop sustained release tablets of Atomoxetine Hcl with view to

prolong the drug release and to give the action of drug for long duration and to avoid non-compliance of it. *In vitro* release of sustained release tablets for batch AH4 was found to be 99.23%. From the overall observation and study of physical properties, *In vitro* study it complies with IP standard for sustained release dosage form, tablet of AH4 selected as optimized formulation.

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